

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

**NANOSPONGES: NOVEL STRATEGY FOR TARGETED DRUG
DELIVERY SYSTEM: A REVIEW****Kaur Navdeep*, Kumar Sandeep**Department of Pharmaceutics, Amar Shaheed Baba Ajit Singh Jujhar Singh Memorial
College of Pharmacy, Bela (Ropar)**Article Received:** June 2020**Accepted:** July 2020**Published:** August 2020**Abstract:**

Owing to miniaturisation, dose-depletion, continuous and restrictive liberation of active substances, well established material constancy, the field concerned with advanced nanostructured systems has seen rapid growth in recent years. Nanosponge's invention has become an important step in overcoming the problems of poorly water-soluble drugs which show many traditional formulating complications. Nanosponge is a compact virus sized sponges (250nm-1um) that credibly stuffed by a broad range of medications and travel across the body until it binds with a certain pointed spot and sticks to the exterior and releases the drug in a restrained manner. This review focuses on methods of preparation, nanosponge applications, factors effecting the drug delivery area, characterization of nanospunges. Nanospunges are an essential conveyor that supply active substances as well as therapeutic medicine delivery process in the medicament industry in post-validate clinical trials. These helps to deliver the drugs at the targeted sites without effecting the healthy cells as well as shows less/or no side-effects. Nanospunges review helps to understand the advantages of this new medication method over conventional medication system. By enhancing the solubility of poorly water-soluble drugs these helps to deliver the drugs, orally as well as topically without first pass metabolism. This is the upcoming system of medication.

Keywords: Nanospunges, controlled, drug delivery, cyclodextrin based polymer, targeted.

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Please cite this article in press **Navdeep Kaur et al, Nanospunges: Novel Strategy For Targeted Drug Delivery System: A Review, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(08).**

INTRODUCTION:

Nanotherapeutics is the contemporary bid of nanotechnology that provides the targeted drug delivery system. It is having far-flung influence on science field specially related to medical field[1]. Nanosponges are the nanotherapeutic formulations that help in improving diagnostics and therapeutic procedures. Nanosponges are the porous, about virus sized substances with naturally ablative polymer backbone[2].

Nanosponges are the tiny mesh-like framework that can encapsulate both aquaphilic and aquaphobic drugs into their inner hydrophilic pocket/orifice and outer lyophobic branching[3,4]. Nanosponges have great swelling property that depends on the ratio of the crosslinker to polymer and synthesized as an acidic or neutral[5]. By the hyper-cross linking of cyclodextrin polymer with the suitable crosslinking agent, cyclodextrin based nanosponges can be developed[6,7]. These act as diluent to increase the carrying capacity of the nanosponges[8,9]. Due to their solid nature, nanosponges have been regarded as safe for the oral and invasive routes and their tiny size make them capable for pulmonic and venous delivery of drug through nanosponges[10,11]. These are the three-dimensional spherical bodies with multiple cavities to accommodate drug molecules[12]. Nanosponges have more advantages than nanoparticles as they can resursect easily with the help of various treatments like clean by environment friendly solvent, gentle warmup, clear by noble gases[13]. Nanosponges transfer medicaments near to specific site at restrictive rate. By encapsulating the medication at its heart, nanosponges help in distributing the product at the target location, thereby helping to minimize the adverse effect by monitoring the discharge of medicaments in a regulated and consistent manner[14]. Nanospongel gels retain on the skin for the desired period of time and reduces the side

effects of overdosing and hence increasing the patient compliance and bioavailability of drug[15,16]. Cyclodextrin based nanosponges are too smaller in size and hence help to eliminate the chlorinated aromatic compounds from the water that is present in trace amount. This aims to distribute the medication faster and safer than traditional and other types of delivery systems. The successful guided medication dispensing a hope for many years, however now this one thwarted with complicated chemical science intricate a modern nanosponge system[17]. This is a very effective delivery system. Cyclodextrin-based nanosponges help to boost the solubility of hydrophilic drugs by protecting labile groups with the creation of inclusion and non-inclusion complexes that help to provide the safe release of drugs at the target position of action[18]. Nanosponges use the water as the transporting fluid by dissolving themselves in water but retain their chemical structure without any modification. It helps to transform liquid to solid and serves as a possible carrier for drug delivery. Particles of nanosponges are dissolvable in water, so nanosponge embodiment can be accomplished through the application of the chemical known as ancillary reagent[19,20].

NANOSPONGEL MECHANISM

The enthusiastic component is brought to vehicles within the entangled shape considering the truth that nanosponges own open structure. The encapsulated drug substance is loosened to move in or out from the particles into the vehicle till the balance is come to. Once the medication is applied to the pores of the skin, the drug substance that's as of now in vehicle gets to be unsaturated, subsequently aggravating the balance. This unsettling influence begins float of drug fixings from nanosponges particle into vehicle from it, to skin until dissolvable is either dried or retained. After that, the surface of the stratum corneum containing wipe particles will proceed to discharge the drug substances on the skin, advertising an amplified discharge over time[19].

NANOSPONGES BUILDING MATERIAL [21-23]:

FEATURES OF NANOSPONGES [24-27]:

- Nanosponges are permeable, innocuous and steady at all temperature till 300°C.
- Mean diameter is less than 1µm although fractions below 500nm in size.
- The ability of nanosponges to load depends mainly on the degree of crystallization.
- These create a smooth and transparent suspension on suspending in water.
- These form complexes for implementation and non-implementation of specific drugs.
- These have three-dimensional structure that help to collect, transfer and effectively discharge a number of substances.
- These are solid and spongy in nature.
- As amphiphathic by character, Nanosponge capable to bear the pair of lypophilic and hydrophilic particle within the spaces between the different moieties of cyclodextrin at the same time.
- Nanosponges help for enhancing the solubility of imperfectly or highly hydrophobic medicaments by holding these within its core.
- These act as the nanocarriers for the biomedical applications.
- Nanosponge formulations stay stable at pH level 1-11.

ADVANTAGES OF NANOSPONGES[28-31]:

- These are biodegradable, calmative, non-killer.
- These are innocuous, non-poisonous.
- Hydrophobic pills encapsulated inside the nanosponges which give Controllable and predictable release of drug that provoke targeted drug delivery.
- Easy scale up for industrial manufacturing.
- Increased reliability, improved elegance and strengthened formulation flexibility.

- Drug compositions may be modified from fast to slow release, avoiding over- or under-dose therapy.
- Over the range of pH 1to 11 and temperssature up to 300°C, these formulations remain stable and secure from degradation.
- Most of the vehicles and drug components are well suited to these formulations.
- Their common pore dimension is 0.25µm the place where micro-organism cannot penetrate, makes these formulations self-sterilized.
- Nanosponges may be labelled with different connections to attack unhealthy cells, thereby attaining substantial effectiveness thus declining negative impact, amount and duration of dosing.
- These increased patient acceptance as compared to conventional dosage form.

DISTRIBUTION OF NANOSPONGES [32-34]:

These are one of the critical sort-of nanosponges that can typify or consolidate the sedate parts in its middle. With the technique of complexation of medicaments, the nanosponges can be distributed into three classes as:

- **Encapsulating nanosponges:** These are amalgamate sort-of nanosponges that encapsulate the medicaments in its middle while it contains many holes such as alginate nanosponges.
- **Complex nanosponges:** These involve the electrostatic charges to attract the drug molecules.
- **Conjugating nanosponges:** These involve strong covalent bond for binding of drug with the nanoparticles.

METHOD OF PREPARATION:**1. Emulsion solvent diffusion method [35,36]:**

2. Ultrasound assisted synthesis [37-39]:

4. Drug loading mechanism in nanosponges[43-45]:

FACTORS INFLUENCING NANOSPONGE FORMULATION:

- i. **Polymer and Crosslinker:** Polymers and crosslinkers have serious impact on the formulation and drug release kinetic of nanosponges. As polymers help in the development of uniform and required sized particle of nanosponges and crosslinkers provide three dimensional nanoporous structure to nanosponges that results in modified release rate of drug. Accommodation of drug molecule of particular sized nanosponge is confirmed by the suitability of cavity size in inclusion complex. Hydroxy propyl β -cyclodextrin has good affinity to form inclusion complex as compared to α , β and γ -cyclodextrin[2,32].
- ii. **Drug:** To make complex with nanosponges, drug should have various features like its molecular weight should be 100-500 dalton, should have not more than five condensed rings, water solubility should be less than 10mg/ml and melting point below 250°C. Its polarity, size and structural properties also effect the interaction between drug and nanosponges[46,47].
- iii. **Temperature:** Alteration in temperature effect the stability of nanosponges. Increased temperature causes the weak interaction forces between nanosponges and drug that makes them unstable[33].
- iv. **Method of preparation:** Capacity of nanosponges to load the drug and to form the complex with drug mainly depends on the method of their formulation. Effectiveness of the method of preparation can be affected by the nature of drug, polymer and temperature[48,49].
- v. **Degree of substitution:** It also affects the nanosponges formulation and complexation with

drug. Higher the degree of substitution, higher will be the cross-linking that results in highly nanoporous nanosponges with mesh like structure[50].

- vi. **Medium of interaction:** Medium used that perhaps be lipophilic and hydrophilic, effect the interaction between drug and nanosponges. A hydrophilic medium takes the organic guest particle into hydrophobic depression, whereas an organic solvent dissolves the organic molecules which are held by the nanosponges[51].

CHARACTERIZATION/ ASSESSMENT

1. **Microscopic study:** To analyse microscopic aspects of medicine, nanosponge and system (Medicine / Nanosponge complex), Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) may be used. The disparity in the crystallization condition of the raw materials and the sample presented under an electron microscope indicates the structure of the inclusion complexes. The nanosponges and complex surfaces were examined using an electron scanning microscope (SEM; Quanta W (FEI Company)). Double-sided adhesive tape was used to install the powdered pellets onto the stubs. The samples were sputter-coated in an argon atmosphere with platinum-palladium (80:20) and examined at a voltage acceleration of 15 kV. A Philips CM 10 transmission electron microscope was used to examine the suspension of complex to elucidate the shape and size of the particles. NIH(National Institutes of Health) picture analysis was used to calculate particle scale[52,53,46].
2. **Particle size analysis:** Free-flowing powders with good graphical qualities can be produced by manipulating the particle size during

polymerisation. The measurement of particle size of loaded and unloaded nanosponges will be performed using laser light diffractometry or Malvern Zeta sizer. The cumulative percentage of drug release from nanosponges of various particle sizes is measured to time to study the impact of particle size on the release of drug. The particles having size between 10 to 25 Å are preferred for the final formulation because particle size greater than 30Å creat the gritty feel[54,36].

3. **Zeta potential:** An fundamental marker of colloidal scattering steadiness is zeta potential. A high zeta potential will confer stability for molecules and particles that are small enough, i.e. the solution or dispersion will resist aggregation. Zeta potential is a calculation of the charge on the rock. This can be calculated using additional electrodes in the equipment with particle size. Samples of the nanosponges were diluted with 0.1 mol / L KCl for zeta-potential calculation and put in the electrophoretic cell where an electric field of around 15 V / cm was added. . Zeta sizer is used to detect the charges on the surface of nanosponges[54-56].
4. **Void fraction/porosity:** Void fraction investigation makes for testing the width in the nanoholes and nanopores that are made. A helium pycnometer measures the porosity of nanosponges, since helium gas can invade associate- and intra-specific channels of fabric. The genuine amount of the fabric is measured by means of the helium uprooting cycle. Since of its permeable presence, nanosponges display more noteworthy porosity relative to guardian polymer utilized to make the gadget[57,19].

$$\% \text{void fraction} = [((\text{Bulk volume} - \text{True volume}) / (\text{Bulk volume})) \times 100]$$

5. **Loading efficiency:** Loading capacity related to nanosponges can be measured by using UV spectrophotometers and high-performance liquid chromatogram methods to quantitatively measure the product loaded into nanosponges. This is achieved by using the entire amount of medicament measured by the centrifugation or gel filtration cycle to remove the untrapped medication. The loading efficiency (%) of nanosponges may be calculated as follows[37,58].

$$\% \text{Loading efficiency} = (\text{Actual drug content in nanosponges} / (\text{Theoretical drug content})) \times 100$$

6. **Production yield:** By measuring the original raw material weight and finished nanosponges, production yields can be calculated. It is estimated by the following equation[54,59].

$$\% \text{ Production yield} = (\text{Practical mass of Nnanosponges} / (\text{Theoretical mass of Nanosponges}(\text{polymer} + \text{drug}))) \times 100$$

7. **Polydispersity index:** It is an file of thickness , else volume, else variety within the conveyance of molecule estimate. The lowers PDI value of monodispers samples, whereas the higher PDI value reveals a broader distribution of particle size and the polydisperse existence of the sample. The following equation can be used to calculate PDI:

$$\text{PDI} = \Delta d / d_{\text{avg}}$$

Where, Δd is the distribution width reffered as SD and in the particle size data sheet d_{avg} is the average particle size reffered as MV (nm)[60,61].

8. **Resiliency:** Modification of the strength of nanosponges modified to create softer or firmer beadlets. Increased connection ratio with cyclodextrin delays the release rate. For example E.g. Prakash et al. have shown that 91 percent of the quercetine in 45min has lower cross-links with β -cyclodextrine composites, whereas nanosponges with higher cross-links result in continuous release of quercetine for up to 24h. Thus, nanosponges ' resiliency according to the demand is optimized by considering the release as a link with time[62].
9. **In-vitro release study:** The dissociation chamber or dialysate membrane phase decides the release of the drug from engineered formulations of nanosponges. Aliquots are removed from the receptor compartment at fixed intervals of time and replaced with fresh receptor solution to maitain sink condition and analyzed by a UV spectrophotometer, HPLC or GC-MS system. Such as 900 ml of phosphate buffer pH 6.8 was placed in the vessel and the type II USP device (paddle method) was assembled. The medium had been allowed to settle at a temperature of $37 \text{ }^\circ \text{C} \pm 0.5 \text{ }^\circ \text{C}$. Prepared Nanosponge powder was put inside the vessel and worked at 75 rpm for 12 h. Filtered and spectrophotometrically analyzed 5 ml of the receptor fluid at definite time intervals[62,63].
10. **Diffractometry with X-ray:** Powder X-ray diffractometry feasibly utilizes for observing complexation of inclusion in solid state. If the drug molecule is liquid, considering the fact that liquid has no diffraction sample of its own, then the sample of diffraction of a newly fashioned substance obviously varies from that of uncomplexed nanosponge. This diffraction pattern difference is indicative of the complex formation. When the drug product is a solid substance a distinction must be made between the diffractogram of the expected complex and that of the drug and polymer molecules '

mechanical mixture. A diffraction pattern of a physical mixture is often the sum of those of each component, whereas the pattern of diffraction of complexes is apparently different from each constituent and leads to a "new" solid phase with different diffractogram. The diffraction peaks for a mixture of compounds are useful for determining chemical decomposition and complex formation[46,64].

11. **Infra-red spectroscopy:** Infra-Red spectroscopy is utilized to test the contact linking Nanosponge and the atoms of drugs within the strong state. Nanosponge groups too as it were move possibly as multiplex shaping happens and where the rate of the visitor particles typified within the multiplex is littler than 25%, groups that will be connected to the parcel of the visitor particles are promptly clouded by the Nanosponge continuum groups⁵². This approach quantifies the association of the medication molecules with the nanosponges in strong state. The downsides related with this method incorporate failure to identify complicated incorporation and the peak characteristics restricted to carbonyl or sulphonyl bunches as it were. The characteristic peak of the non-hydrogen-bonded O – H stretch displayed by β -cyclodextrin FTIR spectra at 3450cm^{-1} is attributed to the existence of essential alcoholic groups. The cross-linking process contributes to depletion of the main alcoholic peak by nanosponge. The typical carbonyl group peak of 1775cm^{-1} in diphenyl carbonate moved to 1750cm^{-1} , and other peaks of cyclodextrin nanosponges within the run $1460\text{--}1600\text{cm}^{-1}$ and $1270\text{--}1290\text{cm}^{-1}$ were observed. Due to the atomic interaction between the medicate and nanosponge, the FTIR spectra showed an expansion or change of the drug peak when the drug was loaded into nanosponge[65-67].
12. **Drug content:** Formulation is taken in a volumetric flask of 100 ml that contains 50 ml of methanol and stirred for 30 minutes. The amount was of up to 100 ml of methanol. 1ml of the above solution has been further diluted to 10 ml by 6.8 pH phosphate buffer. Determining drug content by taking UV Visible spectrophotometer to calculate absorption[68,69].

Table 1: catalog of medicaments encapsulated in Nanosponges

s.no.	Drug	Route	Reference
1	Dexamethasone	Oral, parenteral, dermal	70
2	Tamoxifen	Oral	71
3	Itraconazole	Oral, Topical	72
4	Atorvastatin	oral	73
5	Paclitaxel	Parenteral	74

APPLICATIONS

1. **Nanosponges for drug delivery:** Nanosponges are in a position to carry hydrophobic medicaments (BCS Class-II drugs) with benefits due to their nanoporous nature. These compounds may be used to improve the rate of deterioration, solubility and drug consistency, cover undesirable tastes by transform liquid substances to solids. Nanosponges based on β Cyclodextrin are reported to convey the pharmaceutical three to five times more proficiently than coordinate infusion at the target location. The nanosponges are strong in nature and can be fabricated as the Verbal, Parenteral, Topical or Inward breath dose shapes. The multiplex may be managed for verbal organization in a network of capsules or tablets suitable for the planning of additives, solvents, greases, and anticancer specialists. The complex can be helpfully verbalized in refined water, salt or other fluid substances, for parenteral organization. For topical organization able to effectively be blended into the topical hydrogel[75,76].
2. **Nanosponges as a defense mechanism against deterioration or light:** Gamma-oryzanol is a mixture of ferulic acid ester, has recently attracted considerable interest as a natural antioxidant and has commonly been used to stabilize food and pharmaceutical raw materials, in addition as a sunscreen in the cosmetics industry. The use is restricted by the high photodegradation and instability. Gamma-oryzanol has been encapsulated in nanosponges, showing a strong photodegrading safety. The nanosponges treated with gamma-oryzanol were formulated with a gel and an O / W emulsion[77,78].
3. **Enhancing medication stability:** β -CD units are coupled with polymers, where a number of β -CD units are attached to the same polymer chain. Many units of β -CD make the drug complex more stable. Moreover, the polymer may cooperate in stabilizing the complexes with the β -CD moieties. These studies have been carried out on proteins and peptides due to their inadequate stability, costly development, immunogenic and allergic capacity, and low bioavailability and protease sensitivity. Bovine serum albumin (BSA) proteins are not soluble in solution, and are stored in lyophilized form. On lyophilization, however, proteins can be denatured reversibly and adopt conformation that is markedly different from the native structure. One major drawback in the formulation and production of proteins is the need to preserve their native structure during processing and long-term storage. Proteins such as BSA were well

encapsulated in swellable cyclodextrin-based poly (amidoamine) nanosponges in the nanosponge-based approach, and increased their stability[79-81].

4. **Modulating drug release:** The crucial snag of almost all current available delivery systems is regular administration. A drug loaded in the structure of the nanosponge can however be stored and released slowly over time. Hydrophilic CD NS can change the rate of release of drugs, which can be used to enhance drug absorption through biological barriers, acting as a potent drug carrier in formulations for immediate release. Hydrophobic CD NS can serve for water-soluble drugs, including peptide and protein drugs, as sustained release carriers. Nanosponges can also be used as drug carriers, such as doxorubicin (an anticancer drug), and they can protect the medication when passing through the stomach. The drug is released very slowly at pH 1.1, whereas if the pH is increased to 7.4, release is faster[82-84].
5. **Solubility enhancement:** The poorly water-soluble drugs can influence formulation efficiency. Nanosponge is the carrier network that encroaches the drug into its heart and provides improved solubility as well as formulant bioavailability. Inclusion complex of the cyclodextrin approach is widely used for improving the solubility and bioavailability of lipophilic drugs in pharmaceutical field[85,86].
6. **Nanosponge as a guide to chemical:** Nanosponges which are the "metal oxides" type act as a chemical sensor used in highly sensitive hydrogen detection using titanium nanosponge.

Initially, the nanosponge structure has no contact point, resulting in less obstacles to electron transport and higher 3D interconnection of titanium nanosponges, which is sensitive to H₂ gas[87-88].

7. **In antiviral therapy:** They may be useful for eye, nasal, and pulmonary routes of administration. Nanocarriers may undergo selective delivery of antiviral drugs to the nasal epithelia and lungs to combat viruses that infect the RTI, such as respiratory syncytial virus, influenza virus, and rhinovirus. In nano delivery systems, the drugs formulated are zidovudine, saquinavir, interferon- α , acyclovir, nelfinavir, etc[89-91].
8. **In cancer therapy:** Nanosponges were thought to be three to five times more successful in diminishing tumor development compared to coordinate infusion as the supply of anticancer drugs. Nanosponges target the cancer cells specifically without any harm to healthy cells, that is the biggest advantage of nanosponges over chemotherapy and other treatments for the tumor destruction[92-94].
9. **Engulfment of gases:** Three specific/unique gasses, such as 1-methylcyclopropene, oxygen, and carbon-dioxide, may be encapsulated within cyclodextrin-dependent nanosponges. Oxygen-filled nano-sponges provide oxygen to the hypoxic tissues present in different diseases. Such formulations may controlledly store and release oxygen. These may be a valuable method for potential distribution of other vital gases[95-97].

Patent report on Nanosponges [98-104]

Patent/App. No.	Applicant	Title
W02003/041095 A1	Alberto Bocanegra Diaz	Process of composites preparation between particulate materials and cyclodextrin and/or their derivatives
WO2006/002814 A1	Francesco Trotta, Wander Tumiatti, Orfeo Zerbinati, Roberto vellaro	Ultrasound-assisted synthesis of cyclodextrin.
WO2009/003656 A1	Sea Marconi Technology di Vander Tumiatti S.A.S Francesco Tretta, Vander Tumiatti, Roberta Cavalli, Carlo Maria Roggero, Barbara Mognetti, Giovanni Nicalao Berta.	Cyclodextrin base Nanosponges as a vehicle for antitumoral drugs.
W02012/147069 A1	Universita' Degli Studi Di Torino Francesco Trotta, Pravin Shende, Miriam Biasizzo.	Method of Preparing Dextrin Nanosponges.
US2017/0152439 A1	Lian Kun, Rouge Baton, LA(US) Lian Kun, Rouge Baton	Nanoparticles, Nanosponges, Methods of synthesis, Methods of use.

WO2019/202148 A1	Roquette Freres Francesco Trotta, Fabrizio Caldera, Elisabetta Cattanco.	Cross-linked starch-based polymers for drug delivery.
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CONCLUSION:

Nanosponges are the small sized particles having sponge like structures. These help to entrap both hydrophilic and lipophilic medicaments hence enhance the dissolution of hydrophilic medicaments by encapsulating medicaments within its core or matrix. This is the developing drug delivery system that show too much success in delivering the drugs at the target site which is not easy by the conventional delivery system. It shows more patient compliance as compared to conventional drug delivery system. Nanosponges is the developing segment for the advancement in the treatment of life threatening diseases. It is the upcoming system for the betterment of pharmacy field.

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